

**INFLUENCE OF RETIREMENT ANXIETY ON SOCIAL ADJUSTMENT OF POTENTIAL RETIREE
TEACHERS IN PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN GWOZA EDUCATION ZONE,
BORNO STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

Retirement is a significant life transition that can have a profound impact on an individual's social, emotional, and financial well-being. As teachers approach retirement, they may experience anxiety related to financial security, social isolation, and adjustment to a new lifestyle. This study focusing on influence of retirement anxiety on social adjustment of potential retiree teachers in senior secondary schools in Gwoza Education Zone, Borno State, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey design and the population of the study is all potential retiree teachers in Gwoza Education Zone. The sample comprises of 298 potential retiree teachers. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire title "Retirement Anxiety of Potential Retiree Teachers Questionnaire (RAPRTQ)". The questionnaire was administered to all the 298 potential retiree teachers. The data collected was scored on 4-point Likert Scale and the result were analysed using mean and standard deviation. The finding of the study revealed that potential retiree teachers, agreed that after retirement they will embark on some social adjustment strategies like helping people in their various community, drawing closer to God, adjust their spending, adjust to the limitation of opportunities after retirement and embark on activities that would make them enjoy retirement among others. Base on the finding, it was recommended, among others, that the Zone should provide potential retiree teachers with access to retirement planning resources, such as retirement planning workshop, online resources, and one on one counselling sessions.

Keywords: Retirement Anxiety, Social Adjustment, Teachers, Gwoza Education Zone

INTRODUCTION

Retirement is a significant life transition that can have a profound impact on an individual's social, emotional, and financial well-being. As teachers approach retirement, they may experience anxiety related to financial security, social isolation, and adjustment to a new lifestyle. Work is the essence of life, without work, life will be dull and meaningless. Petters (2017) opined that people work to earn a living, by means of remunerations, to cater for one's daily needs. Others work for financial security, especially working with government, where at the end; there will be retirement benefits in form of pension and gratuity. Some are self-employed while others work to serve humanity. Whatever motivation is given for people to absorb in any type of job or the other, there comes a time in one's life when having put in the mandatory number of years in service, retirement will end that period of service. Retirement is a meaningful occasion in a people's life time. It

implies end of the individual's work period of life and the beginning of another one. To certain individuals, the years in retirement might be longer than those of youth and pre-adulthood. This period accompanies overwhelming difficulties if not decidedly ready for, the change to retirement relies upon monetary conditions, disposition, wellbeing, the response and conduct of friends and family and companions. It also involves acclimation to build recreation time, decline salary age, increment wellbeing concerns and changes in personality and relational relationship.

In Nigeria, it is common knowledge that many retirees face a lot of stress, bitter experiences and challenges. Many wait for years without getting their benefits. Some die even in the course of undergoing the numerous and rigorous screening exercises conducted by the government and other employers without getting the benefits, some are retired without preparation and pre-information. All these results in many problems which in turn creates a lot of anxieties and challenges to the near retired and the retired Uzoekwe & Okafor, (2017). The civil service rules which contain the conditions of service for civil servants stipulate policies and guidelines on employment, promotion, discipline and retirement of workers in Nigeria. It stipulates the length of service and the age of retirement. It comes after reaching the expected retirement age of 35 years in service or 65 years in age in most establishments. How the individuals view this life's transition from work to retirement is influenced by their attitude.

Attitude toward retirement could be positive or negative depending on how prepared the person retiring is ready for retirement. Some retired staff may view retirement as a time of rest after putting in meritorious years in service. Others may see it as a time of hopelessness, loneliness, while others perceive it as a time to socialize, build up relationship and leisure. Retirement is a big and important life event; for some people it is a welcome event, it is a welcome development and a celebrated event world-wide if it occurs at the due time. It implies reaching a meritorious climax of a duly rewarded end of service which attracts send-off parties, church thanksgiving celebration, benefits such as pensions, goodwill speeches, gratuity and allowances. The word retirement, according to Merriam Webster Dictionary, means to withdraw from or stop a job or career because you have reached the retirement age. Musa (2022) explained that, to some people retirement is seen as the end of a life that is happy. Others look at it as the end in which they cannot in any way be useful.

Studies were carried by experts as regards to retirement anxiety on potential retirees in various regions with different views. According to a recent study by Wang and Shi (2020), retirement anxiety is a common phenomenon among older adults and can have a negative impact on the mental health and well-being. The researchers found that retirement anxiety was associated with increased levels of depression, stress, and reduced life satisfaction among retirees. Johnson et al. (2019) suggested that retirement anxiety may be linked to fear of the unknown and a loss of identity and structure that comes with the transition from work to retirement. Individuals who have a strong attachment to their work identity may struggle with the idea of retiring and may experience anxiety as they navigate this major change. According to Ode cited in Dalhatu (2017), some of the major causes of retirement anxiety are inadequate fund, challenges in managing mental health, challenges in managing a new social status, inadequate planning for retirement, difficulties in time management, total dependence on present salary, problem of securing residential accommodation, ignorance of what to do with pension money, attitude of friends and families and the challenges of the sudden retirement, which include: Inadequate Fund, Challenges in managing mental Health and Change of Managing a New or Lower Social Status return to the occupational niche they occupied for so long.

Cultural norms and retirement rules can also affect people's perceptions of retirement and increase anxiety, besides, the timing and circumstances of retirement, such as early versus late retirement or voluntary versus involuntary retirement

can affect the degree of anxiety associated with retirement. When treating retirement anxiety, and customizing therapies to address each person's unique needs and concerns, counsellors must take these various elements into account (Nwankwo, 2020). Counsellors can adapt interventions to changing requirements and support long-term well-being in retirement by routinely assessing coping mechanisms and adjustment levels (Nworgu, 2020). Counsellors need to consider these cultural nuances and provide culturally sensitive support and guidance to retirees as they navigate social adjustments in retirement. By addressing these various dimensions of social adjustment, counsellors can help retiree's foster positive social connections, meaningful roles, and a sense of well-being in their post-retirement lives (Adeyemo & Olatomide, 2021).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Retirement anxiety can lead to concerns about financial security, loss of identity, social isolation, and uncertainty about the future. These factors can significantly impact an individual's mental health and overall well-being. Furthermore, social adjustment plays a crucial role in how individuals and community engagement can influence one's ability to cope with retirement related changes and challenges. Understanding how potential retiree teachers in Gwoza Education Zone experience retirement anxiety and social adjustment is vital for developing tailored counselling interventions to support their transition into retirement, in this context, the study aims to explore influence of retirement anxiety, social adjustment, of potential retiree teachers in Gwoza Education Zone.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study is to examine the influence of retirement anxiety on social adjustment of potential retiree teachers in Gwoza education zone in Borno State, specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

- i. determine the social adjustment of potential retiree teachers in public secondary schools in Gwoza Education Zone;
- ii. assess the various challenges facing potential retiree teachers in public secondary schools in Gwoza Education Zone;

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- i. What is the social adjustment of the potential retiree teachers in public secondary schools in Gwoza Education Zone?
- ii. What are the various challenges facing potential retiree teachers in public secondary schools in Gwoza Education Zone?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is based on Bandura's social cognitive theory (1986). According to Bandura's social cognitive theory, individuals learned through observing and imitating other, as well as through the consequences of their own actions. This theory emphasizes the importance of cognitive processes, such as attention, motivation, and memory in learning and behaviour change. The unique feature of SCT is the emphasis on social influence and its emphasis on external and internal social reinforcement. SCT considers the unique way in which individuals acquire and maintain behaviour, while also considering the social environment in which individuals perform the behaviour. The theory takes into account a person's past experiences, which factor into whether behavioural action will occur. A crucial paradigm for comprehending retirement anxiety and the necessity for counselling among prospective retirees is a social cognitive theory (Olatomide, 2020). This theory explores how people and their social contexts interact in complex ways. People who are

getting close to retirement age, for example, could feel more stressed and unclear about their identities and future roles outside of the workforce.

Concept of Retirement Anxiety

Retirement anxiety is a psychological phenomenon characterized by feelings of worry, unease, and distress related to the transition from the workforce into retirement. As individuals approach retirement age, they may experience a range of emotions and concerns regarding their financial, social relationships. Retirement anxiety is often developed as a result of the thought of retirement and its challenges. Potential retirees in most cases develop retirement anxiety unconsciously which can be perceived through their performances, Retirement anxiety is developed out of fear of uncertainty situation about the future that ambiances the retirement transition. The negative perception of retirement due to poor or lack of adequate preparation for it, are some of the causes of retirement anxiety. Despite the fact that retirement provides opportunity to do all other things hitherto one had little time to do, the change or rather transition is usually not that easy to bear by many retirees. Many potential retirees fear retirement during their working years, because of over dependence on the job. Another reason that makes potential retirees not quit or rather fear retirement could be linked to the joy of a conditioned, routine where a person's life is organized around a particular job for a long period; this makes potential retirees delay their retirement by changing their date of birth (Wang & Shi, 2020)

Causes of Retirement Anxiety

As people approach retirement age, retirement anxiety is a prevalent occurrence that can be caused by a multitude of internal and external reasons, among the reasons are:

- i. **Financial concerns:** concerns about one's ability to maintain financial security in retirement are among the major contributing factors to retirement anxiety. The fear of not having enough money to sustain one's lifestyles, cover medical expenses, or fulfill other financial obligations can lead to anxiety.
- ii. **Fear of uncertainty:** the uncertainty of what retirement will bring can be anxiety-inducing. Retirement often involves a significant change in income and financial stability. Worries about insufficient financial status after retirement is a significant contributing factor, potential retirees could be concerned about whether their pension and retirement funds will be enough to support their preferred lifestyle and pay for medical bills (Oghogho & Nwankwo, 2022). These worries can be made worse by economic uncertainties like market volatility and inflation rates, which can increase anxiety about retirement savings (Nwankwo, 2020).
- iii. **Social isolation:** retirement can bring about a decrease in social interaction, especially for individuals whose work was a primary source of social connections. The absence of daily interactions with colleagues and a perceive lack of social support can lead to feelings of loneliness and anxiety; retirement anxiety may be exacerbated by the loss of social connections and identity associated with one's job (Osuji & Nweze, 2020). Many people look to their jobs for a sense of accomplishment, purpose, and social standing. Feelings of loss, loneliness, and a lowered sense of self-worth can be triggered by the idea of leaving the workforce and the social networks that have been developed over time (Orhunger, 2020; Ogunshola, 2022). This loss of identity and social connections can worsen retirement anxiety, particularly for people who have a close relationship with their job. Anxiety can also be induced by the expectation of significant life change and the uncertainties surrounding retirement. Retirement marks a major shift from a structured daily schedule to a more flexible way of living among individuals. Individuals may worry about how they will fill their time, find purpose, and adjust to new roles and

responsibilities in retirement. The unknown challenges and adjustments required in post-retirement life can generate feelings of apprehension and stress, contributing to retirement anxiety.

iv. Health concerns and ageing-related worries can fuel retirement anxiety: retirement is often associated with age related health issues. Concerns about declining health, the need for more medical care, or functional limitation can contribute to retirement anxiety (Olatomide, 2020). As individuals age, they may experience health issues or anticipate potential health challenges in the future. Anxiety levels can be raised by worries about deteriorating health, the cost of healthcare, and the ability to leave active, rewarding lives in retirement (Adeoye & Legbara, 2019). These health-related anxieties can be compounded by the need for caregiving responsibilities for oneself or ageing family members, adding further complexity to retirement planning and adjustment (Ugwu & Idemudia, 2023).

v. Cultural and societal expectations around ageing and retirement can influence individuals' perceptions and anxieties about retirement: Societal norms may dictate notions of productivity, success, and leisure in retirement, leading individuals to compare themselves to idealized or unrealistic standards (Petroka & Earl, 2019). Cultural beliefs about ageing, retirement roles, and family dynamics can also shape individuals' fears and anxieties about the retirement transition. Understanding these cultural and societal influences is crucial for addressing the diverse causes of retirement anxiety and developing culturally sensitive counselling interventions to support individuals' well-being during this life transition (Mbah, 2019).

vi. Loss of identity and purpose is another main reason of retirement anxiety: retirement often brings a significant change in an individual's daily routine. Many people derive a sense of identity and purpose from their work and prospect of losing that can cause anxiety. The adjustment to a new routine and finding new ways to create meaning in life can be challenging. Retirement anxiety is a common phenomenon that many individuals experience as they transition from a life of work to a life of leisure, loss of identity and purpose comes as individual is leaving the workforce (Losada et al., 2017) for many, their job provides them with a sense of identity and purpose that is hard to replace once they retire. They may have spent decades building their career, so when that comes to an end, they may struggle to find a new sense of purpose and direction. This loss of identity can trigger feelings of anxiety, depression, and uncertainty about the future. It is important for individuals approaching retirement to start thinking about other source of identity and purpose in their lives, such as hobbies, family relationships, volunteer work, or personal goals. By actively seeking out new ways to define themselves and find fulfilment outside their job, individuals can better navigate the emotional challenges of retirement and create a meaningful and fulfilling post work life. According to Ode cited in Dalhatu (2017), some of the major causes of retirement anxiety are inadequate fund, challenges in managing mental health, challenges in managing a new social status, inadequate planning for retirement, difficulties in time management, total dependence on present salary, problem of securing residential accommodation, ignorance of what to do with pension money, attitude of friends and families and the challenges of the sudden retirement, which include inadequate funding.

Effect of Retirement Anxiety on Potential Retirees

An individual's general wellbeing, mental health and ability to transition to retirement life can all be significantly impacted by retirement anxiety. One of the primary effects is the manifestation of psychological distress, including symptoms such as heightened stress, worry, and rumination about retirement-related concerns. Individual who retired compulsorily might experience some psychological and emotional disorder such as moodiness, unstable behavior, heart disease and a pressing tendency to commit suicide. For other particularly voluntary retirees, retirement, help to remove physical, mental

and emotional pressure of a routine job. They are no longer subjected to instruction from superior officers rather they can now develop independent thinking, creativity and skills for personal, socio economic investment, entering a new challenging or more rewarding career or establishing a self-organized venture (Undiyaundeye, 2020).

According to Baba in Dalhatu (2017) some of the major contributions to psychosocial problems for retirees are as follows: Loneliness from losing a spouse and friends: Inability to independently manager regular activities of living: Difficulty coping and accepting physical changes of aging: Financial stresses from the loss of regular income: Boredom from retirement and back of routine to work: Social isolation as adult children are engaged in their own lives: Feeling inadequate from inability to continue to work, and Frustration with ingoing medical problems and increasing number of medications.

Persistent retirement anxiety can contribute to the development or exacerbation of anxiety disorders, depression, and other mental health issues. These psychological effects can impact retirees' quality of life, relationships, and ability to engage in meaningful activities post-retirement (Adeoye & Legbara, 2019). Moreover, retirement anxiety can manifest in physical symptoms and health complications. Chronic stress and anxiety can contribute to physiological responses such as elevated blood pressure, insomnia, digestive problems, and weakened immune function (Nwanko, 2020; Oghogho & Nwankwo, 2022). Over time, these physical manifestations of anxiety can lead to long-term health consequences and reduce individuals' overall health and well-being during retirement.

Additionally, retirement anxiety can hinder individuals' ability to effectively plan for and navigate retirement transitions Fear and apprehension about retirement can lead to avoidance behaviours, procrastination in retirement planning, and reluctance to make important decisions related to finances, healthcare, and lifestyle changes (Olatomide, 2020; Enitan, 2022). This lack of proactive planning and engagement in retirement preparation can further exacerbate stress and anxiety as retirement approaches, creating a cycle of increased anxiety and reduced readiness for retirement (Okpede, 2020). Retirement at times could result in a reduction of social contact with friends, colleagues, co-workers and sometimes relatives. The reduction in the level of social interaction might lead to many hours of boredom, loneliness, solidarity reflection which sometimes could resulting some anti-social behavior like drinking, smoking other. At times due to limited financial resources, some retirees might not have the courage to associate with old friends while for others retirement gives their family members and friends or to concentrate more on leisure activities, such as going to community gathering visiting, playing games and reading among others (Undiyaundeye, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

The design adopted for the study was the descriptive survey design which was considered appropriate because it is often used to assess thoughts, opinion and feeling of persons. The population of the study involved all potential retiree teachers in Gwoza Education Zone numbering 627. The stratified sampling technique was used to for selecting the respondents from the 23 public senior secondary schools in the zone. The sample comprises of 298 potential retiree teachers. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled "Retirement Anxiety of Potential Retiree Teachers Questionnaire" (RAPRTQ) adapted from Binta and Baba (2020). The instrument was validated by three experts from Guidance and Counselling, Educational Administration and planning and Mathematics Education. The instrument was divided into two sections. Section A had 10 items on social adjustment, while section B had 10 items on challenges facing potential retirees. The responses were score on a 4-point Likert Scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The

reliability coefficient of the instrument was 89 which was seen to be reliable. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer research questions.

RESULTS

Research question 1: What is the social adjustment of the potential retiree teachers in public secondary schools in Gwoza Education Zone?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Social Adjustment of the Potential Retiree Teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Gwoza Education Zone

S/N	ITEM	N	MEAN	STD.DV	DECISION
1	I shall have more time to help people in my community after retirement	298	2.73	1.13	Agree
2	I wish I had started to plan for retirement earlier	298	2.81	0.88	Agree
3	I shall adjust my spending to the monthly retirement pensions	298	3.00	0.94	Agree
4	I shall adjust to the limitation of opportunities after retirement	298	3.36	0.95	Agree
5	I shall embark on activities that would make me to enjoy retirement	298	3.00	1.00	Agree
6	I will miss the stimulation that work gave me after retirement	298	2.87	0.88	Agree
7	I shall develop more time to be closer to God after retirement	298	3.55	0.79	Agree
8	I shall enjoy spending more time with my partner after retirement	298	3.30	0.95	Agree
9	I shall partake in health living activities and programme to stay fit after retirement	298	3.15	0.87	Agree
10	I shall partake in social activities after communities involvement to maintain a sense of purpose after retirement	298	2.97	0.89	Agree
GRAND MEAN			2.76		

Decision rule: Mean 2.50-3.49 as agree, while mean which is less than 2.50 as disagree

From Table 1 with the grand mean of 2.76, the result shows that the potential retiree teachers in Gwoza Education Zone have some social adjustment strategies toward retirement period. This implies that, the potential retiree teachers in Gwoza Education Zone have made some preparation for social connections for leisure activities as they approach retirement period.

Research Question 2: What are the various challenges facing potential retiree teachers in public secondary schools in Gwoza Education Zone

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Various Challenges Facing Potential Retiree Teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Gwoza Education Zone

S/N	ITEM	N	MEAN	STD.DV	DECISION
1	Delay in payment of pension/gratuity is a Problem for retirees	298	3.08	1.11	Agree
2	Poor social policy constitutes a retirement challenges for retirees	298	3.23	0.91	Agree
3	Lack of investment an planning is a challenge confronting retiree	298	3.22	0.80	Agree
4	Financial stress from loss of regular Income	298	3.08	0.78	Agree
5	Lack of personal accommodation	298	2.06	1.16	Disagree
6	Loss of social status, self-identity and self-Esteem	298	2.94	1.02	Agree
7	Frustration with ingoing medical problems and increasing number of medications	298	2.70	1.05	Agree
8	Social isolations as adult children are engaged in their own lives	298	2.66	1.00	Agree
9	Feeling inadequate from in ability to continue to work	298	2.64	0.85	Agree
10	Difficulty coping and accepting physical changes of aging	298	2.59	1.07	Agree
GRAND MEAN			2.82		

Decision rule: Mean 2.50-3.49 as agree, while mean which is less than 2.50 as disagree

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

This study examined the influence of retirement anxiety on social adjustment of potential retiree teachers in Gwoza Education Zone of Borno State, Nigeria. This sub-section deals with the discussion of the major findings from the research questions and the tested formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Findings from research question 1 shows that potential retiree teachers in Gwoza Education Zone of Borno state agreed that after retirement they will embark on some social adjustment strategies like helping people in their various community, drawing closer to God, adjust their spending, adjust to the limitation of opportunities after retirement and embark on activities that would make them enjoy retirement among others. This result support the findings of Olatomide (2022), Nwankwo (2020) and Nworgu, (2020) that retirees often need to redefine themselves beyond their professional roles and find new sources of meaning, purpose, fulfilment in retirement and they may experience shifts in their social circles as they

transition from work-related interactions to more leisure-oriented or community-based activities. It was noticed from literatures that an unplanned retirement results into various problems faced by retirees.

Result from research question 2 shows that most of the challenges faced by potential retiree teachers in Gwoza Education Zone are; Delay in payment of pension/gratuity, Poor social policy, Lack of investment and planning, Financial stress from loss of regular income, Loss of social status, self-identity and self-esteem, Difficulty coping and accepting physical changes of aging among others. The finding is in support of (Oghogho & Nwankwo, 2020). Which state that, worries about insufficient financial status after retirement is a significant contributing factor, potential retirees could be concerned about whether their pension and retirement funds will be enough to support their preferred lifestyle and pay for medical bills.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated the influence of retirement anxiety and social adjustment on potential retiree teachers in public senior secondary schools in Gwoza Education Zone. The findings revealed that retirement anxiety has a significant influence on the social adjustment of potential retiree teachers. And at the same time a significant predictor of social adjustment challenges among potential retiree teachers, potential retiree teachers who experience high levels of retirement anxiety are more likely to experience social adjustment challenges, including loss of identity, social isolation, and decreased social status among others. The findings also highlighted the need for pre-retirement counselling programmes and support groups to address retirement anxiety and social adjustment among potential retiree teachers in public senior secondary schools in Gwoza Education Zone. In conclusion, awareness campaign and workshops should be organized for potential retiree teachers in Gwoza Education Zone, if this is not done, it could lead to life of regret and untimely death of retired teachers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Gwoza Education Zone should establish pre-retirement counselling programmes to support potential retiree teachers in their transition to retirement.
- ii. The Zone should provide potential retiree teachers with access to retirement planning resources, such as retirement planning workshop, online resources, and one on one counselling sessions

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